

care physicians proceeds from the presenting clinical problem to diagnosis. Also, the suggested readings were exclusively radiology texts. Lacking were references to basic, essential texts for primary care providers, such as Goodman and Felson's *Felson's Principles of Chest Roentgenology: A Programmed Text* (Philadelphia, W B Saunders, 1999).

Overall, in spite of its shortcomings, *Primary Care Radiology* is probably one of the best radiology textbooks to date for primary care providers. The writing is clear, the images are excellent, and the price is right. In the future, a greater emphasis should be placed upon the day-to-day diagnostic challenges encountered by primary care providers. The current text is best suited for those interested in an in-depth study of imaging; it is not useful as a reference book.

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Primary Care Radiology. By Fred A. Mettler, Jr, Milton J. Guiberteau, Carolyn M. Voss, and Christopher E. Urbina. 269 pp, illustrated. Philadelphia, WB Saunders, 2000. \$45 (paper). ISBN 0-7216-8333-9.

Primary Care Radiology is a soft-cover, inexpensively priced text that aims to serve as a reference for primary care providers to help guide them in ordering imaging studies. The book contains an introduction followed by eight chapters that break down the subject into organ systems and body regions. The introduction contains references to some excellent Internet Web sites. In each of the following chapters, subheadings include presenting symptoms such as acute abdominal pain, specific radiologic findings such as the solitary pulmonary nodule, and diagnoses such as tuberculosis. Each chapter concludes with a list of suggested readings.

High-quality images are liberally spread throughout the book. The images are clear and have easy-to-read labels and legends. The tables are helpful and logical. I especially appreciated the tables included in the appendix, which addresses the cost of various radiologic examinations and the levels of radiation exposure from several different procedures.

I found the text to be primarily oriented toward radiologists rather than primary care providers. Although the premise of the text is excellent, a greater emphasis on the perspective of the primary care provider would be helpful. For example, the book is structured around anatomy, not presenting symptoms or clinical problems. This approach of moving from an imaging procedure to diagnosis is that of the radiologist. In contrast, the primary